

METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: The paper focuses on the study of non-traditional methods of teaching a foreign language aimed at activating the cognitive process of students and developing communicative communication skills. Traditional teaching methods, methods of problem-based learning as an effective means of teaching foreign languages are considered.

Keywords: traditional teaching methods, non-traditional teaching methods, methods of problem-based learning, teaching a foreign language, the learning process.

Introduction: In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, the method is considered to be the way to achieve the goal, but it is used to designate different paths in scale. The method is called the principal direction in teaching foreign languages, characterized by certain goals, content and principles of teaching (grammar–translation method, direct method, etc.). So, with the grammar–translation method, training was conducted with the aim of developing logical thinking and the ability to read and translate texts. The main attention was paid to the study of grammatical rules as the necessary means in mastering a foreign language, and above all by reading. When teaching by the direct method, the main goal was the development of practical skills to use a foreign language: to understand it, speak it, as well as read and write. The word method denotes a path—a system of learning within a direction that reflects the concept of the author(s) who proposed it (the method Francois Gouin, the Palmer method inside the direct method–direction). The word method indicates a way—a way of orderly interrelated activity of teachers and students within a system, on a technological operation that ensures the interaction of the teaching and learning parties and is

included as a component in the learning technology directly related to the problem of how to teach, assuming that the organization and implementation of the pedagogical process takes place: through teaching methods implemented in methodological techniques; using a variety of teaching tools; using various organizational forms of work students; taking into account the age of students, their level of training in a foreign language and general development, degree of training, educational material and time, assigned to its study. The methodology of teaching foreign languages is a system of knowledge about the laws of the process of teaching a non-native language and about ways to influence this process in order to optimize it. The methodology of teaching a foreign language(s) reveals and substantiates the laws of teaching a foreign language.

Traditional and non-traditional methods of teaching a foreign language

It is impractical to talk about the methodology of teaching a foreign language using any one type of speech activity, within the framework of a small message, since all types of speech activity are closely related, do not exist separately from each other. Therefore, we should talk about the problem as a whole.

It is known that the method is always aimed at a specific goal and must be adequate to this goal. Currently, the main goal of all programs is the formation of foreign language competence, i.e. the development of a personality capable of communicating in a foreign language in written and oral speech. The classical model of educational interaction, i.e. the learning process itself in the lesson looked like this: T – starts a conversation, S – answers, T – evaluates. A new type of TBL (Taskbasedlearning) interaction is training based on the formulation of a communicatively conditioned task. In the system of the communicative method, the purpose of teaching is the use of speech activity (speaking, reading, listening or writing) as a means of communication. The primary methodological rule is the constant speech practice of students.

The word method is defined as the way to achieve the goal. The main methods should include:

- introduction (introduction of language material)
- training (in use)
- application (use in speech activity).

First, we will focus on methods for the formation and development of phonetic, lexical and grammatical skills, and then on the development of speech skills.

Phonetics is mainly exercises: listening to a sample and imitation. When developing pronunciation skills, the following organizational forms are used: choral, individual and paired. Phonetic exercises (special training exercises) are used in every lesson. The material can be: individual sounds, sound combinations, words, sentences.

Phonetic charging can precede reading, then it occurs on the material of the reading text. It also happens in connection with the work on new grammatical or vocabulary material. But working on pronunciation should not take much time (this does not apply to the initial period of training).

Teaching the grammatical side.

Grammar is the material basis of speech. The lack of knowledge of elementary grammatical structures precludes adequate reproduction of any text, the correct construction of a speech utterance. There are various methods of introducing grammatical material. You can, for example, suggest a dialogic text: 1 – immediately give a rule after the text is given and students will search for specific material, 2 – or on the basis of text analysis and with the help of leading questions, enter a rule (i.e., use a student research search. Further assimilation of the material occurs during the performance of training exercises. No school textbook contains enough exercises for mastering grammatical material, so additional manuals are used, for example, Golitsinsky Y. Grammar: a collection of exercises, contains a lot of tasks on various grammatical topics. Training is an important principle of mastering grammatical material. Training speech expressions on the topic are used. Control is required. As a final control – testing. There are different types of tests: fill in the gaps, right-wrong, choosing the right answer, give the appropriate form, etc.

Teaching the lexical side of oral speech and reading.

There is a certain arsenal of tools in the method of familiarization with the word. These are, context, synonyms, antonyms; translation into Russian. All these means can be accompanied by the use of visual aids, while translation into Russian may be excluded. It is possible to introduce large arrays of words in dialogical texts in a foreign language with parallel translation.

Reading is a receptive activity, perception and processing of existing text. You can identify certain methods of working with text:

Readingforgist – reading with an understanding of the main content of the text. At the same time, it is necessary to highlight the main idea; choose the main facts, omitting the secondary ones, guess the meaning of words by word-forming elements and by analogy with the Russian language.

Intensivereading –with full understanding;

Reading with the extraction of the necessary information.

Methods of teaching speaking.

It is necessary to use the situation. Situations can be real, imaginary, and even fantastic. The methods of teaching speaking can be various forms of dramatization, including improvisations and role-playing games. There is a division of situations into

standard and non-standard. Standard situations are served by stereotypical language material and they contain much more clichés and clichés. When teaching speaking, it is important to take into account the ratio of its most important forms: monologue, dialogue and polylogue, depending on the number of interlocutors. Although when learning to speak, these forms coexist, often passing into one another.

There are two ways in teaching monologue speech in the methodology:

1 – "way from the top" - when the initial unit of learning is the finished text. The following tasks are recommended:

- read the text by answering questions about the content;
- make a plan of the text in the form of questions or theses;
- to make a program, i.e. to select the necessary material for each item of the

plan. Then there are various retellings of the source material: close to the text, on behalf of different actors, and finally, on their own behalf. The source text can be completely recycled.

2 – "the way from below" - at the heart of learning is a sentence reflecting an elementary utterance. This path involves the deployment of the utterance to a detailed monologue. The simplest situation is when the teacher says, "I love my city. And you?" - the attitude of the students is being clarified. The next stage is that students' statements should include elements of argumentation. When developing monologue statements, you should use game techniques such as: "Build a collective story about a famous person." Someone starts, others continue.

Features of teaching dialogic speech. In the methodology, it is customary to distinguish between standard and free dialogues. Standard dialogs serve typical situations. Most often they assume a clear anchoring of roles (seller-buyer, doctor-patient, etc.) and stereotypical language material (formulas, clichés). Together, they are a mini-dialogue on a household topic, the expressions of which are better to learn by heart.

As for free dialogues, they are of the following types: interview, inquiry, conversation (or exchange of opinions), discussion. Sometimes a remark unfolds, turning into a monologue. The ultimate goal of the dialogue is dialogical communication based on a similar but new situation.

A very common variant of dialogue is a polylogue, a form of speaking adequate to communication in a team. The most suitable method of developing a polylogue is various forms of dramatization, including role-playing games in which a large number of students take part. Moreover, the role-playing game is not based on whole texts. An opportunity for improvisation is created. One of the most natural forms of learning is working in pairs (while not mechanically dividing the class into pairs) and working in

groups (3-5 people temporarily united by a teacher). The work on the development of oral speech is one of the most difficult activities, because it requires a certain level of cultural and intellectual development of students.

Traditional and non-traditional methods of teaching a foreign language - is it possible to draw a clear line between them? What used to be seen as unconventional – all kinds of interviews, theatrical performances, conferences, skits, telephone conversations, investigative journalism, even the organization of the class – has now become the norm in the classroom. All possible teaching methods are aimed at one main goal – the formation of foreign language competence. And going back to the beginning of the report, we can repeat once again that the first methodological rule is the constant speech practice of students.

To give the necessary information and create such conditions that the student has an interest and a desire to express the information they have. The interaction of a foreign language lesson with other subjects is clearly traced. Students, as a rule, are proud when they can show knowledge of other subjects. It is very important to turn the motivational lever.

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